

1 **Immunoglobulin-based therapeutic targeting in breast cancer for the treatment of liver metastasis:**
2 **ANG.**

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7 Metastasis is the major cause of death from cancer and metastasis to the liver is a frequent complication
8 of both breast cancer and colorectal cancer, among the two most common cancers that afflict man (1-5).
9 We recently utilized whole transcriptome technologies to define the full complement of differentially
10 expressed kinases and phosphatases in HER2+ breast cancer: in the primary tumor, and in metastasis to
11 the CNS (6-8). Here we utilize whole transcriptome technologies (9, 10) to conduct drug discovery by
12 measuring total transcription in the liver metastases of humans with breast cancer, comparing the liver
13 metastatic transcriptome to the primary tumor transcriptome. We identify here a therapeutic target based
14 on its differential expression and up-regulation upon metastasis to the liver, ANG, as a candidate
15 therapeutic target for the medical management of liver metastasis using immunoglobulin-based reagents.
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We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms in breast cancer, and adeno and squamous forms of NSCLC in lung cancer, "regional" metastasis to the lymph nodes, metastasis to distant sites, including the lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Here we measure total transcription in metastasis to the liver to discover and describe a therapeutic target identified through rigorous study of the liver metastatic transcriptome in breast cancer: a therapeutic target that is up-regulated and metastasis-specific, providing ideal therapeutic index to minimize toxicity and maximize efficacy: ANG.

Results

Figure 1: ANG is differentially expressed in liver metastasis in humans with breast cancer.

- I. Liver metastases and primary tumors; human breast cancer.

n=19 primary tumors from humans with breast cancer

n=16 liver metastases (tumor) from humans with breast cancer

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
205141_at	4.96E-02	-2.030911	-4.36672	-0.9770981	ANG	1332/52378	97.4

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of the breast and in liver metastases of humans with breast cancer (9), we discovered differential expression of ANG in metastasis to the liver in humans with breast cancer (**Chart 1**). The expression of ANG changed more than 97% of the human liver metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 22,283 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of ANG messenger RNA in liver metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of ANG during disease progression and dissemination in breast cancer.

Thus, differential and increased expression of ANG defines the liver metastatic transcriptome in human breast cancer.

Discussion

Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during treatment with a second agent (whether neoadjuvant chemotherapy or a targeted therapy like trastuzumab). Immunoglobulin-based inhibitors of ANG, once evaluated for toxicity and safety, can immediately be tested for efficacy in patients with liver metastasis who have failed previous treatment, with the ultimate goal of identifying the most effective inhibitors of liver metastasis in humans with breast cancer who have not yet progressed but are predicted to be at high risk, or those whose metastasis has not yet become unmanageable due to metastasis size, number or location. A multi-kinase approach delivered in conjunction with chemotherapies that target dNTP synthesis, replication of the daughter strand and activity at the spindle at anaphase, targeting CDKN inactivation and ATP-binding cassette pump expression in resistant cases, is most likely to be most effective in limiting tumor clone resistance (11).

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References

1. Tsilimigras, D.I., Brodt, P., Clavien, P.A., Muschel, R.J., D'Angelica, M.I., Endo, I., Parks, R.W., Doyle, M., de Santibañes, E. and Pawlik, T.M., 2021. Liver metastases. *Nature reviews Disease primers*, 7(1), p.27.
2. Liu, C., Mohan, S.C., Wei, J., Seki, E., Liu, M., Basho, R., Giuliano, A.E., Zhao, Y. and Cui, X., 2022. Breast cancer liver metastasis: Pathogenesis and clinical implications. *Frontiers in Oncology*, 12, p.1043771.
3. Diamond, J.R., Finlayson, C.A. and Borges, V.F., 2009. Hepatic complications of breast cancer. *The lancet oncology*, 10(6), pp.615-621.
4. Liu, Y. and Cao, X., 2016. Characteristics and significance of the pre-metastatic niche. *Cancer cell*, 30(5), pp.668-681.
5. Milette, S., Sicklick, J.K., Lowy, A.M. and Brodt, P., 2017. Molecular pathways: targeting the microenvironment of liver metastases. *Clinical Cancer Research*, 23(21), pp.6390-6399.
6. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Increased rate of CNS metastasis in patients with HER2+ breast cancer is a result of the intrinsic gene expression program of HER2+ subtype breast cancers, not a consequence of use of the HER2+-targeted drug trastuzumab.
7. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Kinase targeting in HER2+ breast cancer to prevent and treat CNS disease:

1 CDK8.

2 8. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Catalytic site targeting in HER2+ breast cancer for the treatment of CNS
3 metastasis: PPP1R3D.

4 9. GSE124647: Sinn, B.V., Fu, C., Lau, R., Litton, J., Tsai, T.H., Murthy, R., Tam, A., Andreopoulou,
5 E., Gong, Y., Murthy, R. and Gould, R., 2019. SETER/PR: a robust 18-gene predictor for sensitivity to
6 endocrine therapy for metastatic breast cancer. *NPJ breast cancer*, 5(1), p.16.

7 10. GSE56493: Tobin, N.P., Lundberg, A., Lindström, L.S., Harrell, J.C., Foukakis, T., Carlsson, L.,
8 Einbeigi, Z., Linderholm, B.K., Loman, N., Malmberg, M. and Fernö, M., 2017. PAM50 provides prognostic
9 information when applied to the lymph node metastases of advanced breast cancer patients. *Clinical
10 Cancer Research*, 23(23), pp.7225-7231.

11 11. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Therapeutic targeting of catalytically available solid tumor vulnerabilities
12 in human cancer.

13 14 15 16 17 18 19 20 **Methods**

21 We utilized GSE124647 for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in
22 metastasis to the liver and in primary tumors from humans with breast cancer (along with GSE56493 for
23 target validation) using microarray data (published) and R-based computational methods.
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